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*Corresponding Author:-
Hachimenum N. Amadi,
*Department of Electrical
and Electronics
Engineering, Rivers State
University, Port Harcourt,
Nigeria*

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Mitigating Feeder-Wide Blackouts through Optimal Protection Coordination: A Case Study of the Port Harcourt 132 kV Substation

Hachimenum N. Amadi^{1}, Obinna N. Okeke²,
Kingsley O. Uwho³*

*^{1,2,3}Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering,
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria*

ABSTRACT

The study looks at Port Harcourt mains 132kV substation because most medium voltage feeders are faced with blackouts several times per year over the last couple of years, which has caused downtimes during blackout duration, besides the maintenance and operation cost impact. Load flow analysis is used for determining the full load current and determining the Current Transformer's (CT) pick-up current via Newton-Raphson's technique. Short circuit analysis was used to determine the short circuit impedance, short circuit current, and circuit breaker Sizing. Star protection and coordination analysis are used for analyzing the system protection, operation and coordination. After performing the simulation for external fault scenario on three (3) medium voltage feeders: Abuloma, RSPUB 2 and Refinery 1 to evaluate its impact on the existing protection scheme, the result shows that the sequence of operation of the relays for Abuloma and Refinery1 feeder are well coordinated in the sense that the relays downstream from the point of fault tripped first at 316ms followed by the backup relay upstream of the substation at 600ms for an external fault. However, the sequence of operation for the RSPUB 2 feeder is mis-coordinated as the relay upstream of the substation tripped first at 450ms, followed by the differential relay protecting the power transformers (T2A) tripping on an external fault outside the protection zone at 600ms, before the overcurrent relay downstream at the point of fault tripping at 750ms. This means that the entire medium voltage feeder fed by transformer T2A is out of power for a fault that occurred downstream on a feeder. Therefore, a new relay setting coordination is required for the RSPUB 2 feeder. In order to mitigate this challenge, a completely new coordinated scheme was designed using the TCC curve to ensure the coordination starts from downstream of the

point fault (RSPUP 2 Feeder) up to the generator station upstream. Also, the entire definite-minimum-time (DMT) scheme was replaced with the more flexible inverse-definite-minimum-time (IDMT) scheme. The new settings provide a backup for over current fault system that is streamlined and does not result in gross mis-coordination. This work is essential to avoid damage to electrical equipment and personnel working at the station.

Keywords:- *Electrical Transient Analyzer program, Improved relay coordination, Inverse definite minimum time, 132kV Transmission line, Port Harcourt mains*

INTRODUCTION

Protection in power systems is that part of electrical power engineering that deals with safeguarding the power system and its components from faults via the isolation of faulty parts from the rest of the network. The main goal of a system protection scheme is to gain stability in the event of a fault by disconnecting only the faulty component from the rest of the system, while the rest of the network is still in operation [1]. The devices that enhance this scheme of protection are all called protection devices.

These protection devices (PDs) are segmented under current and voltage transformers, circuit breakers, protection relays, communication channels and batteries. The current transformers (CTs) and Voltage Transformers (VTs) are used for lowering the high electrical signals of the power system to a level convenient for the protection relays. The circuit breakers are operated based on the relay commands; the protection relays sense the fault and initiate a disconnection or trip command to the breakers. The communication channels allow the analysis of the electrical quantities at remote terminals of the line and thus permit remote tripping of equipment [2].

Fuses are a set of PDs used mostly in a distribution system. They can sense and clear faults. In order to achieve protection for assets and boost an unbroken electrical power supply, PDs are installed, though failures such as short-circuits, broken or fallen transmission lines, open-circuit, incorrect operation of circuit breakers and insulation breakdown may still occur despite the presence of the PDs. Protective devices, unlike switches, are safe to operate in abnormal fault conditions. There are several protection schemes, namely: overcurrent protection scheme, differential protection scheme, distance protection scheme and directional protection scheme. These are further classified into primary protection and backup protection.

The primary protection is the first line of protection designated for the component parts of the power system. For instance, in the event of a fault on a line, the relay and circuit breaker of the line are intended to act first. The line relay and circuit breaker form the main protection of the line. However, the main protection may fail due to failure of the circuit breaker, tripping circuit, protective relays, current/voltage of supply to the relay or DC tripping voltage supply. When such a failure occurs, the back-up protection will be

initiated. The back-up protection backs the main protection whenever there is a failure in the operation of the primary protection. The back-up protection has to be coordinated with the primary protection such that it has to be slower in operation, thus allowing the primary to operate first.

In order to reduce outages to the barest level, protection coordination is employed [3]. Protection coordination is the method of finding the best fit timing of fault clearing under abnormal conditions. Protection coordination is done by first dividing the power network into zones, so that when a fault occurs, the aim will be to isolate that fault zone from the entire system, so as to minimize the degree of the outage experienced. A zone of protection is a separate zone that is formed around each network components.

The importance of the protection zone is such that any fault occurring within that zone will be taken care of by the relays, thus, relays actuating the opening of the circuit breakers within the zone. Since the breakers are fixed at strategic and suitable locations, every component of the network can be disconnected for repair or maintenance purposes and also in abnormal conditions. There are overlapping zones of protection, done to enhance complete protection for all element of the system, thereby avoiding dead spot. Dead spots are considered to be the unprotected areas in the power system. The essence of zones overlap is to prevent dead spots in the power system [4].

Overcurrent relay coordination is a systematic study of current responsive devices in an electrical power system that seeks to find the ratings and settings of fuses, breakers, relays and other PDs, as well as isolating faults on overloads. Coordination limits the extent and duration of service interruption by selectively isolating faults, thus providing alternative

circuits. Overcurrent relay coordination studies require the preparation of an accurate single-line relay diagram, obtaining the available system current spectrum and finding the equipment protection guidelines. The appropriate devices and their settings are selected, which are then used to plot damage curves and device characteristics curves.

The faults that befall transmission lines have never been an unusual phenomenon, according to Ref [5]. The Artificial Neural Network (ANN) was used to analyse the 132kV transmission line from Enugu to Yandev via Oturkpo. The research discovered the presence of three line-to-ground, three line-to-line, three double line-ground and one three-phase fault. To test for the accepted ANN, performance and regression analysis graphs of output versus target were used.

So long as fault occurrence in the power system is unavoidable, the importance of limiting such faults cannot be over emphasized, as fault occurrence dwindles economic and other sectors' activities. The effects and damages due to fault occurrence in a power system were highlighted by fault analysis done on a 330kV transmission network. The report indicated the nature of the system when three-phase faults were created in three buses of the system (Bus 4, Bus 16 and Bus 23). The results showed that double-line-to-ground faults at the Bus created a phase imbalance, with two lines at each bus experiencing a loss of voltage and the third line experiencing an overvoltage condition [6].

A proper relay selections, settings, performances and coordination were achieved after Ref [7] evaluated three-phase fault currents in a 28-bus 330kV transmission system. They developed two different MATLAB-based programmes. One of which was for load flow studies

that determined pre-fault conditions for the network based on the Newton-Raphson method. The other determined the three-phase short circuit current magnitude on the system. The Effurun 3 x 60MVA, 132/33kV transmission substation network has been investigated by [8].

They used ETAP software to analyze the network and observed that the main cause of the problems facing Effurun transmission station was due to the use of only definite minimum time (DMT) and grading by time overcurrent protection schemes. To solve the problem, they chose inverse Definite Minimum Time (IDMT) relay and grading by both time current overcurrent protection scheme. The scheme was modeled by discriminating from downstream to upstream.

The coordination of working time of the overcurrent relay (OCR) incoming and OCR feeders on a substation with a 60MVA 132/33kV transformer, supplying four (4) feeders, has been studied [9]. It was shown from the analysis that the standard inverse characteristics had the best performance. Relay coordination covers the idea of discrimination between normal, abnormal and fault conditions.

In faulty conditions, relays in the primary protection should be able to act fast, so as to ensure maximum protection and minimum system disruption. In the upgrade of Trans-Amadi 33KV network for protective relay coordination, short-circuit calculation technique was used for protection device selective to enhance the

quick isolation of the affected portion of low-voltage and medium-voltage industrial and commercial power system [10].

None of the previous researchers have worked on practical ways on how the settings of the relays of Port-Harcourt Main substation could be achieved for proper coordination in ETAP software therefore, this work focuses on designing the Port-Harcourt Mains 132kV transmission station in ETAP 20 software environment, to simulate the current relay settings used in Port-Harcourt Mains 132kV transmission station, to identify from the protection point of view feeders with miss-coordinated relay sequence of operation based on the current relays settings; and to improve the coordination settings of relays currently used in Port-Harcourt Mains 132kV transmission using over-current relay time current curve.

Description of Existing Network

The Port-Harcourt Mains is a transmission substation consisting of 3x60 MVA power transformer with Ten (10) outgoing feeders, namely: Abuloma, Rumuodumaya, Woji (RSPUP1), Trans-Amadi (RSPUB2), Rainbow, Refinery2, Rumuola, Refinery1, Airport and Akani.

The substation receives power supply from Afam power station located in Okoloma-Afam in Oyigbo Local Government Area of Rivers State through a 132kV double circuit transmission line of Bison ACSR 350mm² conductor. The single-line diagram of the existing Port-Harcourt Mains transmission substation is shown in Figure 1 below.

Fig.1:-Single Line Diagram of AFAM_PH Mains 132kV Transmission Network (Source: Transmission Company of Nigeria)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The materials used for the study include: Single Line Diagram (SLD) of Port Harcourt Mains TCN substation, Load Data, Current Transformer Data, Overcurrent Relay Data, Differential Relay Data, Software: Electrical Transient Analyzer Program (ETAP 20) Software.

Methods

Load flow analysis was used for determining the full load current and determining the Current Transformer's (CT) pick up current via Newton-Raphson's technique.

Short circuit analysis was applied for determining short circuit impedance, short circuit current, and circuit breaker Sizing. Star protection and coordination analysis were used for analyzing the system protection, operation and coordination.

Substation Component Specification

There are two basic sensing devices used in every protection scheme: circuit breakers and protective relays. The protective devices are interconnected to power equipment such as transformers, loads, motors, generators, etc., whose % impedance percentages are used for fault analysis. Their values are given in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Table 1:-Power Transformer Specification (Source: Transmission Company of Nigeria)

S/No	ID	Voltage Ratio	MVA
1	T1A	132/33	60
2	T2A	132/33	60
	T3A	132/33	60

Table 2:-Current Transformer Specification (Source: Transmission Company of Nigeria)

S/N	ID	Current Ratio
1	CT1	400:1
2	CT2	400:1
3	CT3	400:1
4	CT4	400:1
5	CT5	400:1
6	CT6	400:1
7	CT7	400:1
8	CT8	400:1
9	CT9	400:1
10	CT10	400:1
11	CT11	1200:1
12	CT12	1200:1
13	CT13	1200:1
14	CT14	400:1
15	CT15	400:1
16	CT16	400:1
17	CT17	1000:1

Table 3:-Overcurrent Relay Specification on 33kV Feeders (Source: Transmission Company of Nigeria)

S/N	Feeder	CT ratio	Plug Setting	Time Setting (s)
1	Abuloma	400:1	0.3	0.53
2	Rumuodomaya	400:1	0.3	0.53
3	Woji (RSPUB1)	400:1	0.3	0.53
4	(RSPUB2)	400:1	0.3	0.53
5	Rainbow	400:1	0.3	0.53
6	Refinery 2	400:1	0.3	0.53
7	Rumuola	400:1	0.3	0.53
8	Refinery 1	400:1	0.3	0.53
9	Airport	400:1	0.3	0.53
10	Akani	400:1	0.3	0.53

Short Circuit Impedance of the Grid Network is given by

$$Z_r = \frac{U^2}{S_{sc}} \quad (1)$$

where

U : phase to phase before point of fault in kV

S_{sc} : short circuit power in MVA

Short Circuit Impedance of Transformer 1 is given by

$$Z_{t1sc} = \frac{U^2}{S_{t1}} * \%Z_{t1} \quad (2)$$

where

U: phase to phase before point of fault in kV

S_{t1}: rating of transformer T1A in MVA

Z_{t1} : impedance of transformer T1A in %

Short circuit impedance of transformer 2 is given by

$$Z_{t2sc} = \frac{U^2}{S_{t2}} * \%Z_{t2} \quad (3)$$

Where

U: phase to phase before the point of fault in kV

S_{t2} : rating of transformer T2A in MVA

Z_{t2} : impedance of transformer T2A in %

Short circuit impedance of transformer 3 is given by

$$Z_{t3sc} = \frac{U^2}{S_{t2}} * \%Z_{t3} \quad (4)$$

Where

U: phase to phase before point of fault in kV

S_{t3} : rating of transformer T3A in MVA

Z_{t3} : impedance of transformer T3A in %

Total Short Circuit Impedance is given by

$$Z_{sc} = Z_r + \frac{Z_{t1} * Z_{t2} * Z_{t3}}{Z_{t1} + Z_{t2} + Z_{t3}} \quad (5)$$

Short Circuit in kA is given by

$$I_{sc} = \frac{U}{\sqrt{3} * Z_{sc}} * 10^{-3} \quad (6)$$

where

U : phase to phase before point of fault in kV

Z_{sc} : Total short circuit impedance

Determination of Current Transformer (CT) Sizing

Operating Current (I_L)

The operating current (I_L) of the CT is given by

$$I_L = \frac{S}{\sqrt{3} * U} \quad (7)$$

where

U: phase to phase in kV

S: Transformer rating in MVA

2.3.7.2 Rated Current (I_{pr})

Rated current (I_{pr}) is usually greater than or equal to the operating current (I_L) for the installation. For metering and usual protection, the rated primary current should not be greater than 1.5 times the operating current. Current transformers should be able to withstand 1.2 times the rated current on a constant basis to avoid too high temperature rise in the switchgear installation. Therefore, the rated current is given by

$$I_{pr} = 1.2 * I_L \quad (8)$$

Where

U: phase to phase in kV

S: MVA rating of protected equipment

CT Ratio

$$CT\ ratio = \frac{I_{pr}}{I_{sr}} \quad (9)$$

where

I_{pr}: CT rated primary current selected from the nearest value in market

I_{sr}: CT rated secondary current which is 5A for local use and 1A for remote use

Determination of Protective Relay Sizing

Full Load Current (I_L)

The operating current (I_L) of the relay is given by

$$I_L = \frac{S}{\sqrt{3} * U} \quad (10)$$

where

U: phase to phase in kV

S: MVA rating of protected equipment

Relay Current Setting

Current setting of a relay is set at 120% of the operating current (I_L) which is giving by

$$I_{setting} = 1.2 * I_L \quad (11)$$

Relay Pickup Current (I_{pu})

$$I_{pu} = \frac{Relay\ Current\ setting}{CT\ ratio} \quad (12)$$

Fault in Relay Primary Coil

$$Fault\ in\ Relay\ coil = \frac{Short\ Circuit\ Fault\ Current\ (kA)}{CT\ ratio} \quad (14)$$

Plug Setting Multiplier (PSM)

$$PSM = \frac{Fault\ in\ Relay\ Coil}{Pickup\ Current} \quad (15)$$

Relay Time Dial Multiplier

$$TDM = \frac{T}{\left[\frac{A}{(PMS)^P - 1} + B \right]} \quad (16)$$

where

T: operating Time

PMS: plug setting multiplier

A=19.61, B=0.491, P=2 from IEEE

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results from the protective device sequence of operation obtained in ETAP 19.1 star-protection module are presented and discussed below. For this study, only an external fault which occurred outside the transformer protection zone was considered for simulation.

Determination of Protective Device Sequence of Operation

It is crucial to have a foreknowledge of how relays operate in a given system in order to correct any mal operation for effective protection and service delivery. Table 4 displays the existing relay coordination as used in this study.

Table 4:-Base Case Coordination Status for External Fault

Fault Scenario	Feeder under study	Protective Device Sequence of Operation	Coordination Status
External Fault	Abuloma	R1 tripped at 316ms followed by a backup relay R17 at 600ms. CB1 tripped by R1 at 376ms and CB17 tripped by R17 at 683ms.	Well-coordinated
	RSPUB 2	R17 tripped at 450ms followed by relay R12 at 600ms then R4 at 750ms. CB17 tripped by R17 at 533ms. CB15 and CB12 tripped by R12 at 620 and 630ms respectively. While CB4 tripped by R4 at 810ms.	Miss- coordinated
	Refinery 1	R8 tripped at 316ms, followed by a backup relay, R17, at 600ms. CB8 tripped by R8 at 376ms and CB17 tripped by R17 at 683ms.	Well-coordinated

Table 4 shows the base case coordination status for a three-phase external fault. RSPUB 2 feeder sequence of operation is mis-coordinated as the relay (R17) upstream of the substation tripped first at 450ms, followed by the differential relay (R12) protecting the power transformers (T2A) tripping on an external fault outside the protection zone at 600ms, before the overcurrent relay (R4) downstream at the point of fault tripping at 750ms. This means that the entire medium voltage feeder fed by transformer T2A is out of power for a fault that occurred downstream on a feeder. The correct sequence of operation is that the

feeder relay (R4) must trip first followed by the bus section relay (R17) delayed by at least 150 milliseconds. The differential relay (R12) protecting the power transformer (T2A) ought not to trip on an external fault outside the protection zone. Therefore, a new relay setting coordination is required for the RSPUB 2 feeder. CB17 was tripped by R17 at 533ms, CB15 and CB12 were tripped by R12 at 620ms and 630ms respectively and CB4 was tripped by R4 at 810ms. Figures 2 and 3 below show the sequence of operation report and plot for RSPUB 2 feeder.

Time (ms)	ID	If (kA)	T1 (ms)	T2 (ms)	Condition
300	R12		300		Phase - 87
320	CB15		20.0		Tripped by R12 Phase - 87
330	CB12		30.0		Tripped by R12 Phase - 87
594	R17	2.141	594		Phase - OC1 - 51
677	CB17		83.0		Tripped by R17 Phase - OC1 - 51
1297	R4	8.266	1297		Phase - OC1 - 51
1357	CB4		60.0		Tripped by R4 Phase - OC1 - 51

Fig.2:-Sequence of Operation on RSPUB 2 Feeder

Fig.3:-Plot of Sequence of Operation on RSPUB 2 Feeder

Improved Relay Coordination for Fault on RSPUB 2 Using Time Current Curve

Fig.4:-TCC Plot for Improved Relay Coordination on RSPUB 2 Feeder

Figure 4 shows the time current curve (TCC) plot of improved relay coordination on the RSPUB 2 feeder. The TCC curve is important in achieving proper protection coordination among the protection devices in the network, as it shows the response of the device to various levels of overcurrent. A completely new coordinated scheme was designed. The TCC curve in Figure 4 ensures the coordination starts from downstream of the point fault (RSPUB 2 Feeder) up to the generator station upstream. Also, the entire definite-minimum-time

(DMT) scheme was replaced with the more flexible inverse-definite-minimum-time (IDMT) scheme. The result is that the new settings provide a backup over the current fault system that is streamlined and does not result in gross mis-coordination. The lower portion of the curve on the time axis is the instantaneous trip function. The purpose of the instantaneous trip is to open the circuit breaker quickly on high magnitude fault currents. Figures 5 and 6 below show the improved sequence of operation report and plot for RSPUB 2 feeder.

Time (ms)	ID	If (kA)	T1 (ms)	T2 (ms)	Condition
316	R4	8.266	316		Phase - OC1 - 51
376	CB4		60.0		Tripped by R4 Phase - OC1 - 51
641	R17	2.141	641		Phase - OC1 - 51
724	CB17		83.0		Tripped by R17 Phase - OC1 - 51

Fig.5:-Sequence of Operation on RSPUB 2 Feeder

Fig.6:-Plot of Sequence of Operation on RSPUB 2 Feeder

CONCLUSION

This study examined improved relay coordination in the 132kV Port-Harcourt transmission station. When the primary protection fails the backup protection must intervene to isolate the fault to avoid equipment damage. Load flow analysis was used for determining the full load current and determining Current Transformer's (CT) pick-up current via Newton-Raphson's technique.

Short circuit analysis was applied for determining short circuit impedance, short circuit current, and circuit breaker Sizing. Star protection and coordination analysis was used for analyzing the system protection, operation and coordination. It was seen from the simulation that the sequence of operation of the relays responsible for protection was violated at RSPUB 2 feeder relays.

The sequence of operation is mis-coordinated as the relay (R17) upstream of the substation tripped first at 450ms followed by the differential relay (R12) protecting the power transformers (T2A) tripping on external fault outside the protection zone at 600ms, before the overcurrent relay (R4) downstream at the point of fault tripping at 750ms. This means that the entire medium voltage feeder fed by transformer T2A is out of power for a fault that occurred downstream on a feeder.

Also, the differential relay (R12) protecting the power transformer (T2A) ought not to trip on an external fault outside the protection zone. In order to mitigate this challenge, a completely new coordinated scheme was designed using the TCC curve to ensure the coordination starts from downstream of the point fault (RSPUP 2 Feeder) up to the generator station upstream. Also, the entire definite-minimum-time (DMT) scheme was replaced with the more flexible inverse-definite-minimum-time (IDMT) scheme.

The result is that the new settings provide a backup over current fault system that is streamlined and does not result in gross mis-coordination. The tripping experienced at the substation that caused T2A transformer to be turned off whenever there is a three-phase short-circuit fault on the outgoing 33kV feeders of the transformer has been solved and the over-current protection settings coordination has been achieved successfully, and the sequence of tripping starts at far downstream of the RSPUB 2 feeder relay.

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